

STYLISTIC PROBLEMS OF TRANSLATION OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNIT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4895992>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 20th May 2021

Accepted: 25th May 2021

Online: 30th May 2021

KEY WORDS

translation problems of phraseological unit, stylistic devices, ways of translation, stylistic aspects of translation

Main part

It is well known fact that phrases and idioms are considered as a part of rich and informative art of speech which has been kept by people for many centuries. With the help of phrases speech can be more beautiful, and clearer. However, there are plenty of problems in translation of phraseological unit which have been investigated and still are waiting for the research continuation. Consequently, translation problems of phraseological units into other languages, study the level of their presence in common artistic translation are the most considerable tasks in Translation Studies Science.

One of the most interesting and difficult aspects of the theory of translation is the problem of passing stylistic devices in the target language. The known problem comes into notice of scientists-linguists, and yet is not developed as much as necessary. The importance of studying the way of translation of the figurative devices is determined by the requirement of faithful figurative information passing in any work of art.

ABSTRACT

The main purpose of this article is to learn the stylistic problems of phraseological unit, besides that the information in the article makes us to learn and to analyze the translation problems of idioms. The data will be used as the best methods.

Phraseological units mostly appeared from the people's worldview experience and they can have not any adequate or close equivalent in the second language. For instance fixed phrases are used to indicate symbolic function through the meaning. They can be the followings:

- National distinctive indications; rainy day, black envy...
- Religious conception and notions; the salt of the earth, to fill up the cup...
- Idioms; to twirl the goat horn, to tighten one's belt...
- Phrases that centered on customs and traditions; to recruit somebody

Phrases that based on national-daily philosophy; women's brain, goldfish memory. These kinds of phrases just belong to the any exact nation so to find appropriate and adequate equivalent meaning of them in another language is really tough. It is not enough just to transfer complete meaning of the idioms in the translation but a translator should try to convey national spirit of the fixed phrase.

According to, Anita Naciscione a translator needs to find suitable equivalent. For this purpose, it is very vital to know to the letter and master “background information”, “background knowledge”, a notion and main content of an original, language-stylistic skill of an author, lexical-grammatical system of both languages. A translator must distinguish both two languages and his proper and appropriate translation can raise quality level of translation version.

A translator can use several the methods of passing some stylistic devices that are applied in the source language text to give a large brightness, clarity and expressiveness to the given message. The interpreter may have the following choice: he can copy the device of the source language text to make an effort, if it is not possible; he creates a new stylistic device that has a similar emotional effect in translation in target language. Expressive devices are divided into the following types. They are phonetic, morphological, lexical, phraseological and others. These forms may exist in any language as a system of logical and emotional intensification of the sentence.

The stylistic aspect of translation is necessary to a translator as the faithful and good language translation cannot be formed without it. It is the stylistic aspect of language that is not only responsible for translation from the source language into the target one, but for translator’s skill as well. Foreign language translation depends on a translator’s ability to pass the sense of stylistic units. This is the principle of stylistic compensation, which means a metaphor have to be passed by a metaphor, a metonymy by metonymy, a simile by simile etc. It is the function of stylistic device used in the text that is of essential importance for a translator.

Metaphor

“A metaphor is the interaction between

the logical and the contextual logical meanings of a word which is based on a likeness between objects. For example, in the sentence: "Dear nature is the kindest mother still" Nature is likened to a Mother; i.e. the properties of a mother "nursing, caring for" are imposed on the nature. Thus the metaphor can be defined as the power of realizing two lexical meanings simultaneously”

In metaphor the transference of meaning may take place when there is a similarity in place of location, forms, feelings etc, for example:

“Warm water – “Warm relationship
тепла вода” – тепли стосунки”

“Cold rain – “Cold glance –
холодный дощ” – холодний погляд”

“Foot of boot – “Foot of mountain –
пидошва черевика” пидошва гори”

“Golden watch – “Golden hair –
золотий годинник” – золоте волося”

The previous two examples express the likeness in feelings, the third one shows resemblance in place of location and the last ones demonstrate resemblance in color. “Metaphor can be embodied in all the meaningful parts of speech, in nouns, adjectives, verbs, adverbs, even in prepositions "The leaves fell sorrowfully." In this utterance the adverb that is a metaphor.

“**Metonymy** is a stylistic device based on a different type of relation between logical and contextual meanings, a relation based upon the association of contiguity. Thus the word crown may stand for "king or queen", cup or glass for\ "the drink it contains”. For example:

“Many ears and eyes were busy with a vision of the matter of these placards”. The given sentence logical meanings the words "ears" and "eyes" have contextual meanings - that of people. The relations of two meanings

of the words are based on close interrelations objectively, presented between the part and the body itself. 'Metonymy as other stylistic device is used to achieve concreteness of description. By giving a specific detail connected with the phenomenon, the author evokes a concrete and life-like image and reveals certain feelings of his own. In order to decipher the true meaning of a genuine metonymy a broader context is needed. It is necessary to understand the words in their

proper meanings first. Only then it is possible to grasp the metonymy"

To sum up, there are plenty of problems in translation of phraseological unit which have been investigated and still are waiting for the research continuation. Consequently, translation problems of phraseological units into each other languages, study the level of their presence in common artistic translation are the most considerable tasks in Translation study Science.

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